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BRANDING AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE POSITIONING OF INDUSTRIAL COMPANIES IN THE CITY OF LIMA-PERU

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ABSTRACT

Recent research shows that the purpose of branding is to generate long-term emotional relationships and bonds in consumers, thus being able to achieve loyalty beyond reason to the extent that they provide real value; in the same way create a very important value in the brand to obtain benefits between them; the differentiation of the services with respect to the competition and the obtaining of confidence, reputation and values that are the base for the long term relations with the clients. That is why they are well positioned in the mind of the consumer since each one of them manages to transmit characteristic of its brand towards the acquisition of customers. This means that the competitiveness between companies is increasing as each one of them knows that brands have an impact on their consumers and make their preferences change constantly; Since the brand and the consumer are linked in a subjective way that is to say, the new marketing no longer only sees the physiological needs of the human being but also analyzes and discovers new emotions to be able to position itself in the consumer's mind. Finally, the hypothesis was contrasted with the bump test, a result of 381,157 was obtained with a 5% confidence level. The hypothesis is affirmed. Branding influences the positioning of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

KEYWORDS: branding, competition, trust, consumers, marketing.

INTRODUCTION

In Peru, industrial companies are the lack of implementation of strategies to achieve market positioning, that is to say they are not clear where they want to reach the lack of definition of business objectives and goals; Ignorance of the branding tool, to be able to differentiate itself in the competitive and saturated market is the application of a branding design since in recent years, it began to have greater relevance within the national and international market, [5], [7], in Peru, of the total national trademark registrations, 10% corresponded to education and training; 8.2% to clothing; 7.8% to pharmaceutical products; 6.4% to coffee, cocoa and rice products; 6.3% to advertising services; 5.9% to food and lodging services; 4.5% meat and dairy products; 3.4% medical services and beauty treatment and 3.3% for scientific devices and instruments. Therefore, it can be determined that the brand is a sign that serves to identify and differentiate products and services in the market; or it can be a combination of words, figures, symbols, letters figures, shapes, certain packages, wrappers, and / or combination of these other elements [10], Each brand not only acquires differentiation by name, logo and slogan, but that has been able to position itself in the mind of the consumer by associating each of its attributes. In the same way there is a growth of companies in this area, which are focused on different market segments where each of them must propose strategies that allow it to be sustained over time and be competitive [7], Within this group we find companies industrial in the local market of Lima, they do not have the marketing strategies, it is not positioned in the market, the subscription of the brand in INDECOPI is missing, lack of brand building, identity, differentiation and positioning in the mind of the consumer and Therefore, in such a competent market, knowledge of branding is a key factor in the identity of a business and an important support of commercial strategies, since it allows transmitting the value and differentiation of its attributes in order to position itself in the market, having taken into account the tastes and needs of customers; Therefore, it is necessary to identify the elements of branding that are essential to build a name and beyond that an experience

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that consumers can recognize and adopt in their lifestyle in the short, medium and long term. Therefore, for the application of branding it is necessary to perform an analysis of this, which considers the political, economic, social, technological and environmental factors to know the company's environment, in the same way to perform the SWOT analysis, which will allow us to identify the values and attributes of the personality, implementation of the logo, symbol, the web, etc. [3], on the other hand a study carried out in Chile, mentions that positioning is a strategy that the business world is giving results in recent times of the globalized world in the competition every day is presented with more aggressiveness; the products and services in their eagerness to conquer markets are going through a series of changes that the common man had never imagined. [5], brands have also become a communicational and commercial phenomenon on a scale never before reached in history, transcending and manifesting as an active component of culture [8]

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the research was to perform an analysis on the definition, characteristics and current trends of branding and its link with consumer behavior. It is divided into two parts; the first part addresses the new approach to branding and relevance within global markets and the second part presents some final considerations of the topic, indicating that the brand is a chain of experiences generated over time. The company managed to position itself in the mind of the consumer. The main authors being the companies where it was carried out together with consumers.

METHODOLOGY

Methodologically, the investigation began with the study of brand coaching: It is a tool designed to extract DNA from brands. All team members are certified in Brand Coaching and as Neurolinguistic Programming Practitioners, two learning currents that feed the methodology and make it even more effective. Identity: It is the purest definition of the brand, symbolizes its mission in the lifetime. Without knowing his identity he is only existing, he begins to live when he finds his true purpose. Brand philosophy: The essence of brand identity. Brand Architecture: The composition of the brand and its sub-brands, products or services. Brand Culture: Indications of branding implementation for the entire company. Image: The reflection of identity, something that people can see or perceive. It will depend on both the message sent and the perceptions of the recipient. Naming, Logo Design, Brand Manual, Corporate Design, Product Design, Websites, Social Networks, Illustration and Character Design. Strategy: An action plan ordered in time that will trace the ideal path to fulfill the objective of building the positioning. Branding Strategy: Long-term strategy or creative branding campaign. Experience: Develop brands from their essence in order to differentiate them from the rest. [9]. Then it began with the construction of the instrument based on indicators of the operational table to make the measurement the instrument was applied to 108 respondents. The questionnaire had 15 questions.

The study that was carried out according to the purpose it pursues: It is applied. Taking into account the level of research is: explanatory. The research design is non-experimental, because it was done without manipulating any variable; since it determines when observing phenomena and variables are not manipulated or assign subjects randomly. Like research, it is classified as transectional or transversal since it collects data at a single moment and in a single time; its purpose is to describe variables and analyze the influence and interrelation at a given time. [11]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To give reliability to the instrument, the reliability test was carried out using the SPSS program as a statistical basis, and proceeded to obtain the two halves test, being the result of highly reliable for the tests obtained that are: Cronbach's Alpha, Spearman Brown Coefficient and the test of two halves of Guttman.

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TABLE N° 1:

Internal consistency statistic of the questionnaire, proof of two halves.

Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	,822
		No. of elements	08 ^a
	Part 2	Value	,831
		N of elements	07 ^b
	Total number of items		15
Correlation between forms			,819
Spearman-Brown coefficient	Equal length		,832
	Uneven length		,833
Two halves of Guttman			,842

Source: Questionnaire

General Hypothesis Test: Chi square

Ha: Branding influences the Positioning of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

H0: Branding does not influence the Positioning of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

TABLE N° 2

	Value	gl	Sig asymptotic (2 sides)
Chi-square of Pearson	381,157	100	,004
Likelihood ratio	339,160	100	,060
Linear association by linear	75,545	1	,000
N° of valid cases	108		

Source: Questionnaire

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Taking into account the answers obtained, it is observed that the calculated Pearson Chi square value is (381,157), greater than the Chi table (3,8115). And the asymptotic sig is 0.04 less than 0.05. Where it is affirmed that Branding influences the positioning of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru. On the other hand, for the linear-by-linear association, the calculated Chi-square is 75,545 equally larger than the Chi table, it is stated that there is a linear-linear association between Branding and Positioning.

Specific Hypothesis Test.

H2: Branding significantly influences the market offer of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

H0: Branding does not significantly influence the market offer of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

TABLE N°3

	Value	gl	Sig asymptotic (2 sides)
Chi-square of Pearson	113,107	90	,004
Likelihood ratio	97,460	90	,035
Linear association by linear	26,344	1	,002
N° of valid cases	108		

Source: *Questionnaire*

Taking into account the answers obtained, it is observed that the calculated Pearson Chi square value is (113,107), greater than the Chi table (3.8115). And the asymptotic sig is 0.004 less than 0.05. Where it is affirmed that Branding influences the market offer of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru. On the other hand, for the linear-by-linear association, the calculated Chi-square is 26,344 equally larger than the Chi table, it is stated that there is a linear-linear association between Branding and the market offer.

H1: Branding significantly influences the competition of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

H0: Branding significantly influences the competition of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

TABLE N ° 4

	Value	gl	Sig asymptotic (2 sides)
Chi-square of Pearson	173,107	80	,001
Likelihood ratio	237,460	80	,015
Linear association by linear	85,344	1	,017
N° of valid cases	108		

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Source: *Questionnaire*

Taking into account the answers obtained, it is observed that the calculated Pearson Chi square value is (173,107), greater than the Chi table (3.8115). And the asymptotic sig is 0.001 less than 0.05. Where it is affirmed that Branding influences the competition of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru. On the other hand, for the linear-by-linear association, the calculated Chi-square is 85,344 equally larger than the Chi table, it is stated that there is a linear-by-linear association between Branding and the competition. Branding significantly influences the consumers of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru.

TABLE N ° 5.

H1: Branding significantly influences the consumers of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru

H0: Branding does not significantly influence the consumers of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru

	Value	gl	Sig asymptotic (2 sides)
Chi-square of Pearson	93,127	100	,001
Likelihood ratio	27,460	80	,005
Linear association by linear	8,404	1	,002
N° of valid cases	108		

Source: *Questionnaire*

Taking into account the answers obtained, it is observed that the calculated Pearson Chi square value is (93,127), greater than the Chi table (3, 8115). And the asymptotic sig is 0.001 less than 0.001. Where it is affirmed that Branding influences the consumers of industrial companies in the City of Lima-Peru. On the other hand, for the linear-by-linear association, the calculated Chi-square is 8,404 equally larger than the Chi table, it is stated that there is a linear-by-linear association between Branding and consumers.

When observing the results we realize that the internal consistency of the instrument was highly reliable. Where the values obtained were greater than 0.8. On the other hand, the hypotheses calculated the chi-square calculated were greater than the chi table. (3,8115). Being corroborated with the studies carried out with the brands, they have also become a communicational and commercial phenomenon on a scale never before reached in history, transcending and manifesting as an active component of culture [8]

CONCLUSION

The importance of Branding lies in the fact that it is a process for building brands, it seeks to give value to show all the qualities that brands have in themselves so that the client can know the values and vision that the brand has and that serves to differentiate itself from others. . Since when conducting studies and branding campaigns, it is vitally important to create and position a brand in the minds of consumers in the long run is the brand and everything that is involved such as the logo, color range, name, etc. what endures in the mind of the consumer. All companies before creating a product or service should think about the branding strategies to follow and be constantly monitoring the acceptance or rejection of their brand. Likewise, social networks have become a tool

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not only for the transmission of information, but also for a communication system that allows messages to be transmitted to customers and brands. It is a perfect feedback channel for campaigns, products, this is then the medium, the tool and the channel to be able to do exactly what they want, without invading their space. Currently Branding strategies should be guided to generate positioning to build a better brand of the brand, hand in hand with customers emphasizing their tastes and preferences, trends in current and modern.

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